

Building the EU Cancer and Health Genomics Platform

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Deliverable information

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Revision History			
Version	Date	Comments	Partner
V1	14/09/2023		IC
V2	19/10/2023	Updates from PL	IC
V3	27/10/2023	Updates from PL	IC

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Summary and objective of the deliverable

With the increasing number of targeted therapies approved in the same indication in oncology, and the increasing complexity of tumour profiles, molecular screening programs have been further implemented in clinical routine to facilitate the access to matched therapies via the organisation of Molecular Tumour Boards (MTBs). MTBs have been implemented in several cancer centers worldwide and include different specialists (medical oncologists, haematologists, pathologists, geneticists, medical biologists, computational biologists, pharmacists and radiologists) involved in tumour profiling, molecular alterations' interpretation and treatment decision. However, it can differ widely across MTBs, since no standard procedures, quality requirements or guidelines have been published to date. Standard guidelines and harmonization are still needed.

The Deliverable 8.2 aims to identify national initiatives (WGS) and MTBs with focus on the French initiative and Belgian Precision program aiming to provide country-wide access for cancer patients to diagnosis and treatment.

Work performed

In order to collect information regarding national initiatives in the different European countries, two actions have been carried out:

1. Partners from the consortium were asked to fill a template of 2 pages to collect MTBs organization across countries (Figure 1), including the link to national initiatives in the frame of D8.1
2. Partners from the consortium provided a list of the national initiatives for genome-wide characterization in place in the different countries

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MTB ORGANIZATION

Institution _____

Country _____

Participants to this form _____

Type of MTB _____

General description of MTB
Objectives, frequency, participants and multidisciplinary roles (medical, scientist, management and administrative if relevant), link to national initiatives, engagement strategy for patients ...

Objectives:

Participants & Responsibilities (including administrative & medical management profiles if relevant):

Contact & links:

Frequency:

Engagement strategy for patients:

Samples and data flow
General workflows of both samples and data for the NGS analysis

WP8 - Diagnosis and treatment decision via MTB

Reporting of alterations
Somatic and germline alterations reporting in MTB conclusions

MTB endpoints and follow-up

Synthetic description of the endpoints:

Endpoint categories (please check the following endpoints when relevant to your MTB):

Endpoint category	Endpoint subcategory	MTB endpoints (check when relevant)	Details
Patient/Healthcare professionals	Access to high throughput molecular screening		
	Outcome		
	Access to innovative drugs/trials		
Healthcare providers and administrative	Patient-reported experience measures		
	MTB activity		
Economic impact	Process (workflows and communication)		
	Medico-economic evaluation		

If applicable, which decision support tool (DST) does the MTB use?
(e.g. Clonality, Navis, OC1, Intuzest, SeeOno, etc.)

Figure 1. Template sent to partners of the consortium for MTB organization description

Results

Templates were received completed from 11 institutions (for 13 different MTBs) and 6 different countries, distributed as shown in Figure 2.

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Figure 2. Participants to the questionnaire

Detailed answers of the partners are reported in D8.1

I. National initiatives linked to MTB

The different national initiatives reported by the different partners are detailed below in Table 1. A total of 9 initiatives across 7 countries are reported.

Country	Institutions	Disease/Cancer type	Tumor DNA seq	Tumor RNAseq	Liquid biopsy approaches
Germany	UKSH/UCCSH Campus Lübeck	all	WES/panel	within MTB and research projects	consortial activity: DKTK, DNPM/ZPM; institutional projects

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Germany	Charité Universitätsmedizin Berlin (NCT MASTER PROGRAM)	all	WGS/WES/panel (both custom designed and commercial)	within MTB and research projects	consortial activity: DKTK, DNPM/ZPM; institutional projects
Spain	Consortium (INGENIO)	Lung cancer	NGS panel	Specific cases	Institutional projects
Spain	Univ. Hospital of Salamanca, Cancer Research Center: PETHEMA	Acute leukemias (AML, ALL), Myelodysplastic Syndromes (MDS)	NGS panel	Selected cases	No
France	Plan France Médecine Génomique 2025	8 clinical preindications	WGS/WES	yes	A pilot phase is planned
Belgium	Sciensano/BSMO/BAL LETT & GeNeo lab consortia (PRECISION)	all	CGP (> 500 genes)	yes	Included in GeNeo- 1 (terminated)
Czechia	Institute Hematology and Blood Transfusion	Myeloid malignancies	WES-germinal NGS panel- somatic	Specific cases	microRNAs, exosomes - research only
Poland	Medical University of Warsaw	HEM malignancies, Brain tumors, Ultra-rare tumors	NGS panels - custom designed WES in some cases	Selected cases	Not yet
Italy	ACC MTB WorkGroup (16 officially endorsed MTBs)	Tumor-agnostic, Lung cancer and rare tumors prevalent	NGS panels, WES occasionally	Selected cases	Routinely, from several vendors + outsourcing

Table 1. National initiatives linked to the MTBs among the CAN.HEAL consortium

Conclusion and impact

National genome-wide characterization initiatives are ongoing across Europe. However, the number of countries and regions that are covered by such initiatives are still limited and could be developed across EU to enlarge access to molecular screening to more patients, and consequently increase the access to early phase clinical trials and targeted therapies.

The NGS test used for tumor characterization are genome-wide approaches, which can probably be explained by the diminution of NGS costs and the implementation of national initiative programs.

The data accumulated within the consortium will be key for future initiatives, clinical trials and research exploitation.

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